

CLOSENESS TO THE ORIGINAL TRANSLATIONS OF IBN SINO'S RUBIES IN UZBEK

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Annotation

Poetry translation has its own complex aspects, in which the translator not only translates word for word, but also reflects the tone, weight, rhyme, and especially the author's goal - the idea in another language. should get For this reason, not every translator is engaged in poetic translation. The translation of Ibs Sino Rubaiyats is also very difficult. The purpose of this article is to show the complexity of the translation of Ibn Sina's Rubaiyats from Persian-Tajik and Arabic into Uzbek and to show the analysis of the preservation of originality during the translation process.

Key words: Ruba'i, poetry, translation studies, idea, originality, poetic method, responsibility, heirs of the East.

Аннотация

Стихотворный перевод имеет свои сложные аспекты, в которых переводчик не только дословно переводит, но и отражает тон, вес, рифму и особенно авторскую цель - мысль на другом языке. По этой причине не каждый переводчик занимается поэтическим переводом. Перевод Ibs Sino Rubaiyats также очень сложен. Цель данной статьи - показать сложность перевода рубайятов Ибн Сины с персидско-таджикского и арабского на узбекский и показать анализ сохранения оригинальности в процессе перевода.

Ключевые слова: рубаи, поэзия, переводоведение, идея,

оригинальность, поэтический метод, ответственность, наследники Востока.

After the independence of our republic, a lot of work has been carried out in translation studies, especially in the field of artistic, historical, and translation studies, and this continues. Translation studies is considered one of the complex fields. But within this complex field there is another complex direction that requires not only hard work but also special talent. This is a poetic translation. Indeed, translation is a complex activity, nevertheless, this field is developing day by day, and many of our poet translators are presenting new poetic works to readers.

Uzbek translations of Ibn Sina's Rubaiyat are also bright examples of poetic translation. His Ruba'is were written in Persian-Tajik and Arabic. Ibn Sina's Rubaiyat contains deep philosophical ideas. Because, as our head of state noted, the life and work of Abu Ali Ibn Sina, who was awarded the title of "the most famous philosopher and encyclopedic scholar of the Islamic world and one of the greatest thinkers of mankind", aroused special feelings of pride and respect for generations. This great breed, who started scientific research at the age of 16, created more than 450 works during his lifetime. Most of them are primarily devoted to medicine and philosophy, as well as logic, chemistry, physics, astronomy, mathematics, music, literature and linguistics. Of course, studying the scientific heritage of our great grandfathers, such as Ibn Sina, is one of the important tasks before us, the young generation. As we study Ibn Sina's scientific heritage and translated works, the examples of his rubaiyat are of great importance in our classical literature and in the field of translation studies.

Ibn Sina's Rubaiyat translated into Uzbek is very close to the Persian original. Ergash Ochilov, translation scholar, candidate of philological sciences, gives these thoughts about the translation of Ibn Sina's Rubaiyat: "The appearance of several translations of a certain work is a positive phenomenon in the practice of artistic translation. In particular, there are three translated copies of Ibn Sina's Rubaiyat in Uzbek. At first, Shoislam Shomuhamedov translated 20 of his rubai

along with other poetic works. These Rubaiyats became famous among the people because they were translated in a simple, clear and effective manner according to the original. Sh.Shomuhamedov's translations differ in form even though they correspond to the original in terms of content due to the fact that they are translated in finger weight. Based on this, Jamal Kamal recited Ibn Sina's 30 Rubai'is in Uzbek with his own weight. Despite the relatively high number of Persian-Arabic words and phrases, these translations also found their fans among readers with a high taste and sensitive taste, who are the successors of high Eastern poetry. Every translator wants to try the power of his pen in the translation of great word artists. This opens the way for new translations. These lines are explained by the author's use of the third translation of Ibn Sina's rubai. We translated 46 of his ruba'is into Uzbek in their traditional weight." From the theory of translation, we know that in the implementation of translation from one language to another language, as well as the commonality between peoples, plays an important role.

The closeness of the Uzbek translations of Ibn Sina's Rubaiyats to the original lies precisely in the traditions and commonalities of Eastern poetry and, of course, in the commonality between the Turkic-speaking and Persian-speaking peoples, which have been preserved for centuries. Let us consider this in the example of the following rubai:

*Az qa'ri gili siyoh avchi Zuhul
Kardam hama mushkiloti getiro hal;
Berun chastam zi kaydi har makru hiyal,
Har band kushoda shud, magar bandi achal.¹*

The translation of this rubai by Jamal Kamal in Uzbek language:

*Shul hoki siyohdin to avji Zuhul,
Har nechaki mushkilot erur, etdim hal.*

¹ Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Avchi Zuhul. – Dushanbe, Irfon. 1980, 23-bet

*Ochdim necha zanjir – zanjiru makru hiyal,
Yechdim necha bir tugun, magar qoldi ajal...*

It can be seen that the translation of the Persian rubai in the Uzbek language is the same as the original. Maybe even more. We can easily say that this translation is an equivalent translation. It is as if Ibn Sina wrote the same rubai in both languages. The weight is the same in both rubies. Rhyme in both: zuhal, hal, ajal words. The distance from the earth to the sky is written in verses that attract deep philosophical observation. The poet emphasizes that death is an insoluble problem, both as a doctor and from the point of view of Islamic philosophy. In the original and in the translation, the form and the content do not differ from each other.

*Gar boda gahe xuram, nishone xomist,
Var z-on ki mudom may xuram, badnomist.
May shuhu hakimu rind boyad, ki xo'rad,
V-in har se nay, mayxo'r, ki dushmankomist.²*

We will compare the Rubaiyin in the Persian language with its translation into the Uzbek language and consider their differences and closeness to the original.

*Gar bodani goh-goh icharmen - xomlig',
Ammoki mudom ichar esam - badnomlig'.
May shohu hakimu rind ichar ersa, na xush,
Gar boshqasi no'sh aylasa – dushmankomlig'.³*

(Jamol Kamol tarjimasi)

When we compare the original with the translation, we can see the similarity. But this rubai is not exactly the same as the original as we have seen above. Because there was a change in the weight, there was a difference between the interpretations of the rabbis. In the translation, artistry is expressed more

² Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Avchi Zuhul. – Dushanbe, Irfon. 1980, 26-bet

³ Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Lirika (tarjimonlar: Sh.Shomuhamedov, J.Kamol, A.Irisov). 5-bet

strongly. But the translator's skill in maintaining perfection in terms of ideas and content is worthy of praise.

*Ey nafs, ki bastai hoyu havasi,
Bishtob, ki dar himoyati yak nafasi.
Dunyo matalab, choh macho, ishva mahar,
K-az do 'st baroiyu ba dushman narasi.⁴*

*Ey nafs, ki g'arq ayla havoyu havasing,
Zud o'lki, zarur himoyati bir nafasing.
Dunyo dema, molu davlatu ishva dema,
Kim, do 'st deb dushmanga o'lasing...*

We can see a kind of perfection in both Rubaiyats. Rhymes are also translated with the same weight as the adverbs of language possibility: in Persian, they are formed by adding - ing to the suffix - i in the words havasi, hansu, narasi in Uzbek. As we have compared all aspects, the closeness between the original and the translation is clearly visible in one reading.

*Soqi, qadahi moi maini tu kuchost?
V-on oinai xudoybini tu kuchost?
Hoham ki tahorate diham botirno,
On lo 'lashikasta lo 'laini tu kuchost?⁵
Soqiy, qadahi jur 'ati joning qayda?
Ul oinai nuri jahoning qayda?
Sun mengaki, ko 'nglimni musaffo etayin,
Taqvoni shikast aylagoning qayda?⁶*

The weight was completely preserved in both rubies. Perfection has also been

⁴ Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Avchi Zuhul. – Dushanbe, Irfon. 1980, 30-bet

⁵ Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Avchi Zuhul. – Dushanbe, Irfon. 1980, 27-bet

⁶ Abu Ali Ibn Sino. Lirika (tarjimonlar: Sh.Shomuhamedov, J.Kamol, A.Irisov). 5-bet

preserved in terms of meaning. In general, the original and the interpretation are very close to each other. Unlike other Rubai'is, this Rubai'i preserves radif, which is expressed by the Uzbek word. In conclusion, it can be said that the translation of Ibn Sina's rubai is perfect and very close to the original. The preservation of weight and rhymes in almost all Rubaiyats is a high example of the translator's talent. The form in all the Rubaiyats is -a -a -b -a. As the translation scholar E. Ochilov said, "today there are three forms of Abu Ali Ibn Sina's Rubaiyat, they should be evaluated not as a denial of a denial, but on the contrary, as an effort to create an alternative translation that corresponds to the original both in form and content."

In short, Ibn Sina's Rubaiyat has a very unique content, and the fact that the ideas in it are preserved in the translation is a great success. It is possible to read and understand Ibn Sina's works in Uzbek language through these interpretations and understand his views, opinions and emotions.

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